

Chronic Paraquat Exposure on Kidney and Vitamin E and C Treatment Benefits

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to evaluate the role of vitamin E and C in managing paraquat-inflicted kidney injury in rat. Exactly 120 rats were grouped A-D with 3 sub-groups (0, VE and VEC) of 10 rats each. All "0" subgroups were orally poisoned with paraquat increasing level of 0.0g/Kg, 0.02g/Kg, 0.04g/Kg and 0.06g/Kg for A, B, C and D respectively every two weeks for 3 months. All subgroup VE were orally treated with 500mg of vitamin E weekly for 3 months and all "VEC" subgroups were treated with 500mg of vitamin E and 2000mg/L of vitamin C weekly for 3 months. Blood samples and kidneys were collected at second and third months, the samples were assessed for kidney function. The results showed that singular vitamin E treatment and in combination with C restored renal function in paraquat-mediated nephrotoxicity in rats.

Keywords: *kidney, paraquat, vitamin, urea, creatinine*

1. Introduction

The kidney is a vital internal organ in the body that has quite a lot of essential functions summarized in an acronym called A WET BED which represents: Acid-base balance, water balance, electrolyte balance, toxin removal, blood pressure, erythropoietin production and vitamin D synthesis (Lisa et al., 2016). In a summarized term, the kidney is known for its excretory role and that serves as the basis to assess its function by way of measuring urea and creatinine because it is expected that the kidney should excrete these waste products so when it is high in the blood, it signals an excretory dysfunction of the kidney (Okolonkwo et al., 2023; Fyneyface et al., 2018; Fyneyface et al., 2020).

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The leading causes of chronic kidney disease are diabetes, hypertension and infection (Jeffrey and Peter, 2016). Other causes include drugs and chemicals which have toxicity potentials to damage the kidney. With the rising reports of insecticides, herbicides and other toxic agents induced organ toxicity (Okolonkwo et al., 2022; Amadi et al., 2022; Amadi et al., 2022), there are now increasing interest to study how environmental pollutants affects human health.

In this study, attention was pointed towards paraquat. Paraquat is known to be very useful in killing weeds and as such it is used in agriculture for weed management to promote crop yield (Okolonkwo et al., 2022; Okolonkwo et al., 2023; Okolonkwo et al., 2014). However, although beneficial in weed management, it is enlisted as a harmful herbicide to man. Studies have implicated liver toxicity and other organ involvement in paraquat poisoning (Okolonkwo et al., 2023; Okolonkwo et al., 2014). In this current study, effect of paraquat ingestion on kidney was study and the therapeutic effect of vitamin E and C on the injured rat kidneys.

2. Materials and Methods

Study Design

The experimental study consisted of 120 rats weighing an average of 200g±20g which were grouped and treated accordingly as stated in the table below:

Table 1. Rat grouping

Main groups (30 rats per group)	Sub-groups (10 rats per sub-group)
A	A ₀ = without any treatment A _{VE} = treated only with 500mg of vitamin E weekly for 3 months A _{VEC} = treated with both 500mg of vitamin E and 2000mg/l vitamin C weekly for 3 months
B	B ₀ = treated with 0.02g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months B _{VE} = treated with 0.02g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months and then treated with 500mg of vitamin E weekly for 3months B _{VEC} = treated with 0.02g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months and then treated with both 500mg of vitamin E and 2000mg/l vitamin C weekly for 3 months
C	C ₀ = treated with 0.04g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months C _{VE} = treated with 0.04g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months and then treated with 500mg of vitamin E weekly C _{VEC} = treated with 0.04g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months and then treated with both 500mg of vitamin E and 2000mg/l vitamin C weekly for 3 months
D	D ₀ = treated with 0.06g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months

	<p>D_{VE} = treated with 0.06g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months and then treated with 500mg of vitamin E weekly</p> <p>D_{VEC} = treated with 0.06g of paraquat every 2 weeks for 3 months and then treated with both 500mg of vitamin E and 2000mg/l vitamin C weekly for 3 months</p>
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The rats were obtained from Animal House, Department of Biology and transported to the Department of Chemical Pathology where the study was conducted. The rats were allowed to acclimatize for 2 weeks prior to the commencement of the study.

Paraquat treatment was administered via oral gavage route on the test groups according to the dose-dependent group classification and indicated on the table above. Vitamin E and C were also administered orally.

In the A group, after 3 months, the rats were anesthetized using chloroform and then sacrificed. The blood was collected via cardiac puncture and assayed for urea and creatinine (UC).

In the B group, B₀ was anesthetized and sacrificed after paraquat intoxication but in the vitamin treatment subgroups, second month after treatment, 5 rats were anesthetized and sacrificed from each subgroup and samples collected were analyzed for UC. Similarly, on the third month of treatment, the last 5 rats were anesthetized from each subgroup and samples analyzed for UC. The methods used for the determination of UC parameters are methods described by Okolonkwo (Okolonkwo, 2023)

Statistical analysis

The obtained data were analyzed descriptively as mean±SD and inferential statistics were analyzed as Two Way ANOVA using SPSS version 23.0. The test was considered significant at p-value≤0.05

3. Results

Table 2 showed that there was a significant increase ($p \leq 0.05$) in urea and creatinine levels in a dose-dependent fashion in groups treated with paraquat. After treatment with vitamin E and C, as in single treatment or in combination, there was a significant reduction the urea and creatinine level at the second month of treatment.

Table 3 showed that there was a significant increase ($p \leq 0.05$) in urea and creatinine levels in a dose-dependent fashion in groups treated with paraquat. After treatment with vitamin E and C, as in single treatment or in combination, there was a significant reduction the urea and creatinine level at the third month of treatment.

Table 2. Changes in some biochemical data after two months treatment period.

Groups	Urea (mmol/L)	Creatinine (umol/L)
A ₀	2.40 ± 0.04	2.44 ± 0.12
A _{VE}	2.90 ± 0.07	2.38 ± 0.07
A _{VEC}	3.48 ± 0.09	3.18 ± 0.15
B ₀	8.53 ± 0.09 ^a ,	58.95 ± 1.29 ^a
BE	8.78 ± 0.11 ^{a,b}	37.85 ± 1.38 ^{a,b}
B _{VEC}	7.43 ± 0.09 ^{a,b}	31.15 ± 0.67 ^{a,b}
C ₀	11.60 ± 0.16 ^a	154.43 ± 1.74 ^a
C _{VE}	9.18 ± 0.13 ^{a,b}	35.55 ± 0.26 ^{a,b}
C _{VEC}	7.88 ± 0.08 ^{a,b}	33.43 ± 0.86 ^{a,b}
D ₀	13.78 ± 0.02 ^a	180.75 ± 0.90 ^a
D _{VE}	10.43 ± 0.10 ^{a,b}	97.25 ± 1.74 ^{a,b}
D _{VEC}	9.28 ± 0.08 ^{a,b}	64.11 ± 0.56 ^{a,b}

Statistical significance: P ≤ 0.05

Table 3. Changes in some biochemical data after three months treatment period.

Groups	Urea (mmol/L)	Creatinine (μmol/L)
A ₀	5.45 ± 0.10	4.15 ± 0.20
A _{VE}	2.95 ± 0.09	9.92 ± 0.02
A _{VEC}	3.80 ± 0.09	5.06 ± 0.02
B ₀	10.60 ± 0.28 ^a	97.21 ± 0.31 ^a
BE	10.95 ± 0.13 ^{a,b}	89.71 ± 0.11 ^{a,b}
B _{VEC}	10.00 ± 0.12 ^{a,b}	95.14 ± 0.26 ^{a,b}
C ₀	17.95 ± 0.12 ^a	145.51 ± 5.47 ^a
C _{VE}	16.45 ± 0.07 ^{a,b}	79.28 ± 0.46 ^{a,b}
C _{VEC}	14.25 ± 0.05 ^{a,b}	77.32 ± 0.87 ^{a,b}
D ₀	27.00 ± 0.34 ^a	231.05 ± 5.49 ^a
D _{VE}	20.35 ± 0.25 ^{a,b}	128.30 ± 2.46 ^{a,b}
D _{VEC}	22.20 ± 0.41 ^{a,b}	81.58 ± 0.25 ^{a,b}

Statistical significance: P ≤ 0.05

Figure 1. photomicrograph of the kidney showing Normal (A, B and C) and abnormal (A, B and C) treatment groups [H&Ex400].

Indications: Glomerulus (G), Renal tubules (RT), Bowman's space (BS), chronic dilatation and atrophy of the glomerular tubules (dotted circle) destroyed glomerular tufts (yellow arrows in abnormal slides-ABC) and glomerular tubular necrosis (red star).

“A” in the normal section represents the control group, while “B” and “C” represents groups treated with vitamin E and C after paraquat poisoning

“A, B and C” in the abnormal section represent the paraquat subgroups treated with only paraquat.

4. Discussion

Paraquat exposure caused significant increase in the mean Urea and Creatinine values. The increased levels of blood urea and creatinine may indicate kidney dysfunction. These results clearly showed that PQ has a harmful and stressful influence on the renal tissue, and it is consistent with the report of Lewis and Nemery (Lewis and Nemery, 1995). Zakim and Boyer (Zakim and Boyer, 1982) stated that massive hepatic necrosis as a result of PQ administration caused impairment in the renal function thereby elevating the serum urea, creatinine and uric acid levels. This was also supported by Wershana in 2011, who reported increased urea and creatinine values of PQ treated animals (Wershana, 2001). Oreopoulos *et al.* (Oreopoulos *et al.*, 1968) described a case of a farmer after taking a mouthful of gramaxone (PQ), his blood urea levels were 178 mg/100ml and 310 mg/100ml after 4 and 6 days of PQ ingestion, respectively. Similarly, Shahar *et al.* (Shahar *et al.*, 1980) found that the plasma urea concentration of a 3-year-old boy increased to 60mg/100ml after 4 days of swallowing of a mouthful of 20% PQ solution, his initial plasma urea concentration was 12mg/100ml after 24hrs of ingestion. In experimental animals, PQ induced similar effects; a reduction in renal function has

been reported following PQ administration to mice and dog (Ecker et al., 1975; Davies et al., 1977).

Urea levels can be increased by many other factors such as dehydration, antidiuretic drugs and diet, while creatinine is more specific to the kidneys, since kidney damage is the main significant factor that increases serum creatinine levels (Garba et al., 2007). Therefore, the significant increase in urea and creatinine levels noted in this study is classical sign of adverse effect of PQ administration on kidney (Garba et al., 2007). However, a report indicated that the additive and synergistic interaction may occur with combination of dietary antioxidants against free radical inducing damage in cells and tissues (Hercberg et al., 1998). The present study demonstrates that administration of vitamin E and vitamin C in rats regulated the antioxidant enzymes in a manner that favored the reduction of serum urea ($P < 0.05$ - months 2 and 3) and creatinine ($P < 0.05$ – months 2 to 3) significantly. This was supported by Wershana in 2011 (Oreopoulos et al., 1968) who stated that vitamin C succeeded in preventing the impairment in the renal function. Tai *et al.* (Tai et al., 1985) while adding support, stated that the significant dose-related reductions in feed intake and body weight-gain, and elevation of blood urea nitrogen and creatinine when Simazine (a similar toxin to PQ) was fed to rats, were ameliorated by the pre – and post – treatments with antioxidants (vitamin E and C alone and in combination) emphasizing that antioxidants restored the viability of such cells during a toxic insult.

The histological slide results revealed that paraquat caused glomerular necrosis in the kidney. This implies that the rise in urea and creatinine levels were due to the degenerating glomerular tubules. Murray and Gibson reported that PQ is excreted mainly via the urine and the concentrations of the herbicide in the kidneys are relatively high, predisposing changes like vacuolation of the convoluted renal tubules and proximal tubular necrosis (Murray and Gibson, 1972). The degeneration of the proximal tubular cells has also been confirmed by electron-optical studies. The nephrotoxicity caused by PQ is pronounced and appears to be restricted to the proximal nephron (Ecker et al., 1975). However, in this study treatment with vitamin E as a single treatment or in combination with vitamin C restored kidney function in the rats.

5. Conclusion

It has been identified that paraquat inflicted injuries on the kidney tissue of the treated rats. This poisoning resulted in kidney tissue damage and decline in kidney excretory function in a paraquat dose-dependent pattern. However, the treatment with vitamin E as a single therapy or in combination with vitamin C restored both renal biochemical markers (urea and creatinine) and tissue structure.

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